

Effect of foliar sprays of Zn on the yield and zinc uptake by rice.

Zn source	Concentration of Zn solution (%)	Yield (t/ha)		Zn uptake (g/ha)
		Grain	Straw	
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.10	5.3	9.2	301
	0.20	5.8	10.8	394
Zn-EDTA	0.01	5.4	9.4	231
	0.10	6.0	11.5	350
Zn-chelate (with phenolic group)	0.02	5.0	9.4	202
	0.10	5.6	10.2	310
Control		4.3	7.4	135
LSD (P = 0.05)		0.6	1.2	58

recorded. Grain and straw samples were collected, processed, and analyzed for Zn content.

Rice grain yield significantly increased with foliar sprays of Zn, regardless of Zn source (see table). Higher Zn concentrations increased grain yield, but the effect was significant only for the chelated form.

Zn-EDTA at 0.1% produced the highest yield of 6 t grain/ha, which was

significantly superior to that with ZnSO₄·7H₂O but at par with Zn-chelate. A similar pattern of yield response was observed for rice straw. Zn uptake in rice increased significantly the rates of all the tested sources.

This study suggests that Zn applied as Zn-EDTA is more efficient at correcting Zn deficiency in rice than either ZnSO₄ or Zn-chelate. □

Fertilizer management—inorganic

Long-term effect of inorganic fertilizers, lime, and straw on lowland rice in Kerala

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We are conducting a study of the long-term effects of continuous application of N, P, K, lime, and straw incorporation on lowland rice. This interim report covers the first consecutive 4 yr from rabi (wet season) 1987-88 to rabi 1990-91.

The field experiment has a permanent layout of 40-m² plots in randomized block design with three replications and nine treatments. The soil is a hydromorphic silty clay with initial pH 4.8, EC 0.1 dS/m, 3.4% organic carbon (OC), 7 kg available P/ha, and 100 kg available K/ha. Treatments consist of combinations of 90-20-38 kg NPK/ha and lime, a control, straw incorporation, and soil test recommendation (STR). STRs were 49-23-40-900 kg NPK and lime/ha for the first 2 yr, 82-14-35-1450 for the third yr, and 49-16-40-700 for the fourth yr.

Rice crop was harvested at about 10 cm above ground level. For the straw incorporation treatment, straw was returned to the respective plots after recording yield.

Lime was applied at first plowing, when the straw was also incorporated.

Rice variety Pavizham (MO-6, 120 d) was wet seeded at 100 kg/ha until 1989 kharif (monsoon); thereafter transplanting at 15- × 15-cm spacing was used. Fertilizers were applied as urea, mussoorie rock phosphate, and muriate of potash as per treatment; N and K in two equal splits as

basal and at panicle initiation stage; and P as fully basal. Weeds were controlled by herbi-cides and/or hand weeding.

Pooled analyses of the data revealed that the treatments, seasons, years, and treatments × seasons interactions were statistically significant in grain yield. Variations in grain yield was not significant during kharif (see table). During rabi, all the treatments that provided 90 kg N/ha and STR were statistically on par and produced significantly higher grain yields than the treatments that received no N.

No interactions were statistically significant for straw yield despite significant treatment and seasonal and annual

variations. Straw yield and growth and yield attributes, such as plant height, panicles/m² and panicle weight, varied significantly with treatment and followed grain yield trends, but had no significant interactions.

Soil analyses data showed that treatments produced no significant variation in pH, EC, OC, and available P and K in the soil.

Results show that in the lowlands of Kerala, rice responds to applied fertilizers only during rabi. Among the three major nutrients, only N produced a significant response. Straw incorporation and lime application had no measurable effect on yield. STR overpredicts the need for lime and hence appears uneconomic. □

Effect of inorganic fertilizers, lime, and straw on rice. Kerala, India, 1987-91.

Treatment (kg NPK/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle weight (g)	Available P in the soil (kg/ha)
	Kharif	Rabi	Mean					
Control	2.0	2.4	2.3	2.5	71.8	269	1.96	12.4
Straw alone	2.0	2.5	2.3	2.4	72.2	295	1.89	15.2
90-0-0	2.2	3.0	2.6	3.1	78.3	315	2.32	9.6
90-20-0	2.2	3.4	2.8	3.3	77.3	309	2.24	8.8
90-0-38	2.4	3.1	2.7	3.2	78.0	303	2.27	9.2
0-20-38	2.0	2.4	2.2	2.4	73.5	270	2.18	8.8
90-20-38	2.2	2.7	2.5	3.4	76.7	316	2.35	10.8
90-20-38 + 600 kg lime/ha	1.9	3.1	2.5	3.1	78.9	313	2.27	9.2
Soil test recommendation	2.1	3.1	2.6	3.4	77.3	317	2.37	8.0
LSD ^a (0.05)		0.6	0.5	0.5	4.6	35	0.28	ns

^a LSD to compare treatments × seasons interaction means.

Large granule urea (LGU), an efficient and economic source of N for wetland rice

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The N-use efficiency of prilled urea (PU) in wetland rice is 20-50%. Rock phosphate-coated urea (RPCU), gypsum-coated urea (GCU), and sulfur-coated urea (SCU) are costly to produce: urea supergranules (USG) are expensive to apply. These costs reduce their economic benefit although they supply N more efficiently than PU. LGU is a new